

FEATURES OF METHODS AND TEACHING OF A FOREIGN (ENGLISH) LANGUAGE FOR MEDICAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Karimova Nigora Ikromovna

Independent researcher of the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8288253>

Abstract: This thesis discusses the features and methods of teaching English in medical universities today. It contains information about the role and importance of the English language in professional medicine. Nowadays, the fact that many terms are used in English in addition to Latin and Greek means that it is necessary to learn this language.

Keywords: English for special purposes (ESP), Medical English, medical terminology, professional communication.

Due to the globalization of professional communication processes, the English language is becoming more widespread and important in almost all areas of special knowledge. Communication skills in English are especially in demand in the field of information technology and medicine. Thus, in the medical professional discourse, English began to be widely used already in the second half of the 20th century. Currently, there is a significant increase in the number of English-language scientific publications on medical topics, in addition, 80% of scientific journals indexed in the international Scopus database are also published in English [5].

English is also the official language of most international conferences. In addition, more and more Russian medical specialists are collaborating with professional teams and medical institutions in English-speaking countries, and international internship programs are now becoming more accessible for medical students, which also require communication skills in English and a confident knowledge of medical terminology.

Given all these requirements and challenges that reality throws at us, the need to rethink some aspects of teaching English to students of medicine is becoming increasingly acute. This is explained by the fact that only the full development of competencies that ensure high-quality communication between future doctors and their foreign colleagues in various academic and professional situations is a key factor in the productivity and success of the work of Russian medical workers [1].

As a starting point for rethinking the structure and content of a professionally oriented English language course for medical students, one can take the interpretation of the characteristics of English for Special Purposes (ESP), proposed by theorists of teaching methods T. Dudley-Evans and M. St. John. Scientists divide the characteristics of this type of teaching English into two types - absolute and variable.

The absolute characteristics of English for Special Purposes include the following aspects:

- ASC (ESP) is developed taking into account certain professional needs of students; - courses ASC (ESP) necessarily takes into account the methodological and activity aspects of the special professional industry that it serves;
- in the course of studying the ASC (ESP), students study grammar, vocabulary, registers, communication skills and genre-discursive specifics of the English language, corresponding to the professional field they are mastering.

Variable characteristics of English for Special Purposes include:

- ASC (ESP) can be developed in accordance with specific disciplines of the professional cycle;
- ESP can be used in specific situations, and its teaching methodology may differ from the general practical English course;
- most likely, the ESP course is developed for students enrolled in higher and secondary vocational education programs. However, it is possible to teach ASC (ESP) in specialized secondary schools;
- ESP courses, as a rule, are designed for students with an average or advanced level of knowledge of the English language;
- most of the ESP courses are designed for students with basic knowledge of the English language, but they can also be used in work with learners [3].

Thus, the main purpose of creating a medical English course is to prepare students for certain situations in their professional communication, such as examining a patient, taking a medical history in English, discussing various issues related to the provision of appropriate medical care. In other words, in the course of developing an effective ESP course, first of all, it is necessary to take into account situations of real professional communication with patients and colleagues using the “industry lexicon” containing medical terms, professionalism and jargon [6].

In the course of the practical implementation of the goals set, it is required to include the following tasks in the ESP course for medical students:

- tasks aimed at developing students' speaking skills in the target language; - various discussions, debates and round tables devoted to the discussion of certain problems in the field of medicine;
- tasks that contribute to the expansion of students' professional vocabulary
- acquaintance of students with new industry vocabulary, work on the correct pronunciation of English terms, a comparative analysis of Russian and English medical terminological units and expressions;
- speech tasks that develop students' communication skills with patients in English (alternating questions and answers, advice to patients) using correct grammatical structures, relevant vocabulary and communicative formulas; when performing such tasks, special attention is paid to the formation of linguistic literacy among students;
- assignments, during which students are invited to familiarize themselves with the content of a specialized medical text in English in a limited period of time, find the most important information in it and make a message in English;
- role-playing games and cases simulating situations during which students have to solve certain professional tasks and demonstrate communication skills in English - for example, examining a patient, recording a medical history, etc.

Of course, when preparing and performing the tasks listed above, the level of English proficiency of students should be taken into account. So, in classes with students whose English language skills correspond to the level B1 (or pre-intermediate), more attention should be paid to the development of everyday informal English communication skills, reading authentic texts in English and listening. During the next year of study, it is necessary to develop communication skills for students with such a starting level in a professional medical environment, expand their industry vocabulary and create conditions for the use of medical jargon in speech practice.

As for students with a B2 (or upper intermediate) level of English proficiency, from the first year of study at a university it is advisable to work out with them communicative situations typical for professional communication, discuss issues related to medicine and the health care system, while expanding the sectoral vocabulary of students in relevant grammatical contexts and genres of medical discourse through more complex tasks related to such areas of knowledge as "Medicine", "Pharmacology", "Anatomy", "Physiology", "Pathology", "Therapy", etc. Of particular interest at this stage is the work with terminological units (lexicon and set expressions) of medical discourse, which were formed due to such cognitive mechanisms as conceptual metaphor and metonymy. The study of such a layer of industry vocabulary with the help of conceptual schemes greatly improves the results of its development by students [2].

A significant obstacle in the study of ASC (ESP) by students of medical educational institutions is the fact that this discipline is planned only for the first two years of study. This does not allow to implement the English language course in such a way that it thematically resonates with the disciplines of the professional cycle of the entire educational program.

Certain difficulties in working with students studying a foreign language for special purposes also lie in the fact that the time for preparation can be seriously limited. Additional difficulties for the teacher are created by certain specific requests and needs of students related to the actualization of the English language in the field of highly specialized professional communication. This state of affairs often requires the teacher to develop copyright materials that would fully meet the academic needs of students. The solution of such problems, caused by the specifics of the professional field and the individualization of approaches in education, is possible due to the involvement of various authentic medical documents in English - patient information sheets, medical questionnaires, videos and brochures in English, which are distributed in medical institutions in English-speaking countries from the purpose of conducting educational work among the population, English-language medical websites, television shows that promote a healthy lifestyle, documentaries and feature films in English on medical topics. All of these resources are extremely valuable for developing an appropriate ESP course.

The creation of an ASC (ESP) ("task-based") course focused on the set educational tasks [7] contributes to the formation of conditions favorable for the development and consolidation of foreign language professional communication skills among medical students. Certainly selected tasks allow students to simultaneously deepen their knowledge in the field of medicine and develop skills of professionally oriented speech, taking into account the structural, semantic and pragmatic aspects of the English language, as well as in accordance with the set communicative goals.

References:

1. Kazaryants K.E. Model of the system of didactic quality of the pedagogical process in the university // Bulletin of the Moscow State Regional University. Series: Pedagogy. 2010. No. 1. S. 32-38.
2. Tishchenko S.V. On the question of the metaphorical representation of the construction of the causation of movement // Questions of Romano-Germanic and Russian Philology. 2014.

No. 1. S. 184-194.

3. Dudley-Evans T., St John M. Developments in ESP: A multidisciplinary approach. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1998. 301 p.
4. Foster P. Task-based Learning and Pedagogy // ELT Journal 53 (1999) No. 1. P. 69-70.
5. [Electronic resource]. Access mode: <http://www.researchtrends.com/issue-31-november-2012/the-language-of-future-scientific-communication/> (Accessed 21.05.2018).
6. Spolsky B. Sociolinguistics. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1998. 128 p. 7. Willis J. A Framework for Task-based Learning. London: Longman, 1996. 192p